

RTO, An Specific Crop Ontology for Rice Trait Concepts

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ABSTRACT

Being the greatest significant crop in Asian countries, rice and its breeding have long been a concerned research issues. Unfortunately, a standardization of rice trait ontology has been lacking, and make it challenging to normalize the description of lab results. In this work, a rice trait ontology (RTO) is manually curated by aligning three existed terminology set of rice trait. RTO includes 2,522 rice trait concepts with corresponding descriptors defining relations among concepts. Hopefully RTO standardizes the common-used trait concepts during rice breeding research, and provides the possibility of automated mining of rice traits knowledge. To make it easier for concept query, a user-friendly web service is released via the link, <http://lit-evi.hzau.edu.cn/RiceTraitOntology>.

1 INTRODUCTION

Research on gene-to-trait association has long been a focus for crop molecular breeding. To accurately represent plant trait terms, specific plant-oriented ontologies are needed to be constructed. Gramene(Jaiswal, 2002) (<http://www.gramene.org/>) was the first comparative genome database for cereal crops and rice, which annotated rice (*Oryza sativa*) genomic sequence with phenotypes and associated biological information including molecular markers, mutants, polymorphisms and quantitative trait loci (QTL). Gramene employed the Trait Ontology (PTO, <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-trait-ontology>) to facilitate trait related phenotypic curations, and the Plant Ontology (PO, <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-ontology>) to facilitate the representation of morphological and anatomical feature. The latest version of Gramene(Jaiswal, 2002) has integrated comparative genomics and pathway resources in terms of 1.7 million genes from 44 reference genomes.

To emphasize more in plant phenomics, the Planteome project(Cooper, 2018) (<http://www.planteome.org>) provided a suite of specific ontologies and controlled vocabulary for plants, which integrates key ontologies including PO, TO, Plant Experimental Conditions Ontology (PECO, <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-experimental-conditions-ontology>), and Phenotypic Qualities Ontology (PATO, <https://github.com/pato-ontology/pato>). Ontology specific for crops has also developed, for example, wheat. Recently, Nédellec(Nédellec, 2020) proposed the wheat trait ontology (WTO), an ontology started developing in 2010 and aimed specifically to wheat trait and phenotype information. Unfortunately, there is no specific trait ontology for rice till now.

This research focuses on the development of rice trait ontology and investigation of the rice gene-to-trait association. Till now, there have been developed several main databases curated for rice gene-to-trait associations. OryzaBase(Yamazaki, 2010) was a comprehensive rice database from Rice Annotation Project (RAP), and it assigned TO, PO and gene ontology (GO) designations to mutants which were classified into three growth stages: seedling, vegetative and reproductive.

The purpose of this research is to widely collect rice trait phenotypic concepts among a couple of plant ontologies, developed an integrated rice trait ontology.

In this work, we construct a rice ontology (RTO) by manually aligned three existing terminology set of rice trait. The RTO describes 2,522 rice trait and defines relations between these concept. RTO is suitable for standardizing rice trait in rice breeding research and offers the possibility of automated mining of rice traits knowledge. Meanwhile, for quickly query and use of RTO, a user-friendly web service is released on <http://lit-evi.hzau.edu.cn/RiceTraitOntology>, this web provides basic information searching as well as quick queries of external links for RTO terms. The construction method and principles of RTO is also described in this paper.

2 METHODS

2.1 Construction of Rice Trait Ontology (RTO)

In order to construct a comprehensive rice trait ontology, the basic construction idea is as follows. First, Investigate and select the terminology set that may include the rice traits related terms. For this purpose, 9 terminology set are collected and manually checked, including Plant Trait Ontology, Wheat Trait Ontology, funRiceGene, Rice Ontology, Flora Phenotype Ontology, Plant Ontology, Plant Phenology Ontology, Plant Stress Ontology. Finally, TO, WTO and funRiceGene are selected due to the broad coverage of rice traits and high term quality.

Table 1. Main ontologies used for rice trait ontology construction

Ontology	Total #	For Rice	External Ontologies
PTO	4,824	NA	ChEBI, NCBITaxon, ENVO, PATO, GO, PECO
WTO	596	NA	None
funRiceGene	528	528	None

There are three related ontologies for rice or plant traits. As shown in Table 1, PTO is an early plant ontology which consisted of 1,557 separately developed plant trait concepts and 3,267 external concepts from ChEBI, NCBI taxon, etc. For Wheat ontology, there are 596 specific trait ontology concepts. There are 528 keywords closely related to plant trait proposed in funRiceGene. The current RTO are derived from the above three terminology sets. Among them, TO, being the most widely used plant trait ontology, classifies plant traits into 10 classes, including biochemical trait, biological process trait, plant growth and development trait, plant morphology trait, plant quality trait, plant vigor trait, sterility or fertility trait, stress trait and yield trait. This is a more complete hierarchical for pant trait classification, so this basic structure will also be used for the construction of RTO skeleton. The Wheat Trait Ontology (WTO) is the first crop trait ontology, which contains 596 terms. It also has a special hierarchical structure, including 313 entries for wheat plant phenotypes and 215 terms for environmental conditions. This ontology include many plant traits important for crop breeding, so it is also used for RTO construction considerations. The funRiceGene, a growing database of gene-phenotype associations in rice, has been manually designed with 528 phenotypic concepts specific to rice and important in breeding, and was likewise considered as an important source of RTO entries.

Second. Two funded domain experts are invited to develop the guidelines for the RTO construction through discussions with domain peers, and to complete the ontology construct and quality control together.

In the RTO construction, the Protégé(Musen & Team, 2015) is used to import obo ontology file so that the hierarchy structure of ontology can be visualized and it help experts to perform manual alignment to ontologies. For the consideration of ontology structure and concept coverage, the basic hierarchical structure of TO is used as the skeleton of RTO. Specifically, after anchoring concept in TO hierarchical tree, other ontologies will be manually aligned to this skeleton to complete the construction of RTO. As Shown in Figure 1(a), the alignment was performed with three operations: delete irrelevant concept, add new concept, and merge repeated concept.

- Delete: Deletion is an operation to remove concepts which are not relevant to rice. In Figure 1(b), the "wheat dwarf" concept in WTO, ID of which is WTO:0000366, was directly removed when performing the alignment, since the trait is not relevant to rice. Similarly, there are 62 other traits removed from WTO.
- Add: Addition is an operation to add new concept to RTO. In Figure 1(c), a "grain composition" concept with WTO ID (0000087) was added in RTO, and put under the TO hierarchy of "plant quality trait".
- Merge: Merge is an operation to merge two concepts from TO and WTO and list it to RTO tree. In Figure 1(d), the terms of WTO:0000095 and

TO:0000480 are synonyms "nutrient deficiency". In the TO hierarchical tree, the TO node has father node TO:0000238 "growth media composition sensitivity". In the meantime, the WTO node has a father node, WTO:0000008 "abiotic condition". Comparatively, the TO tree is deeper than WTO. The targeted TO node traces back to the TO root through 4 parent nodes, i.e., TO:0000238, "cell membrane stability", "abiotic stress trait", and "stress trait", while there are only two parent nodes between the target WTO node to WTO root. Regardless the difference of tree depth, TO:0000480 and WTO:0000095 concepts are aligned by removing WTO concept. In addition, WTO:0000095 is recorded in *xref* annotation of TO:0000480.

RTO was curated manually with two funded domain experts. The ontology checking was carried on via Protégé, and the whole construction, curation and checking procedure took 12 months. Eventually, the latest version of RTO was publicized in the form of obo file in the Github project, <https://github.com/bionlp-hzau/RiceTraitOntology>.

Fig. 1. Ontology alignment with TO and WTO. (a) The delete, add and merge to ontology terms in ontology alignment step. (b) “WTO:0000366 wheat dwarf” is deleted in RTO. (c) “WTO: 0000087 grain composition” is added to RTO. (d) “TO:0000480 nutrient sensitivity” and “nutrient deficiency” are merged into the same term.

ID	NAME	DEFINITION	IS_A
WTO:0000586	gladin content	None	WTO:0000583 gluten strength
WTO:0000587	glutenin content	None	WTO:0000583 gluten strength
WTO:0000588	resistance to Khapra beetle	None	WTO:0000269 storage pest resistance TO:0000261 ...
WTO:0000589	yellow rot	None	TO:0000384 nematode damage resistance TO:00003...
WTO:0000590	high molecular weight glutenin subunit	None	WTO:0000587 glutenin content
WTO:0000591	swelling index of glutenin	None	WTO:0000587 glutenin content
WTO:0000592	wheat moth	None	WTO:0000583 Lepidopteran insect
WTO:0000593	Xanthomonas campestris pv. translucens	None	WTO:0000323 fungi WTO:0000297 bacteria
WTO:0000594	high-molecular-weight Ds glutenin subunit	None	WTO:0000590 high-molecular-weight glutenin subunit
WTO:0000595	resistance to Bipolaris sorokiniana	None	WTO:0000599 resistance to Spot Blotch WTO:00005...
WTO:0000596	resistance to Fusarium spp.	None	WTO:0000543 resistance to Crown Rot WTO:000054...

Fig. 2. Data browsing page of Rice Trait Ontology (<http://lit-evi.hzau.edu.cn/RiceTraitOntology/>). (a) Browsing page for basic information of RTO terms. (b) Browsing page for detail information and external links of selected RTO term, in this instance is “carbon sensitivity”.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Statistics of RTO

In the current consolidation, there are 2,522 concepts in our RTO portfolio.

Among them, there are 1,557 overlapping terms between RTO and PTO, 534 overlapping terms between RTO and WTO, 500 overlapping terms between RTO and funRiceTrait. We adopted three integration strategies: delete, add and merge, in which 63 nodes were deleted, 75 nodes were merged and 118 nodes were added. The complete RTO file can be downloaded from the github project (<https://github.com/bionlp-hzau/RiceTraitOntology>).

3.1 Data browsing page of RTO

To provide easily term browsing and external searching of RTO terms, a user-friendly web page is released (<http://lit-evi.hzau.edu.cn/RiceTraitOntology/>).

As shown in Figure 2 (a), the basic information of RTO terms, including term id, name, definition, and IS_A relationship, is presented through the table, and the search box with a recommendation function is used to quickly target the interested term. The complete RTO file can also be downloaded via the download button on the top right of the page.

RTO detail browsing page is presented in Figure 2 (b), more information about and external links of the interested term can be found on this page. For example, XREF for the term’s corresponding concept in other ontologies, COMMENT for the comments of the term from human experts, and SYNONYM for other synonyms or abbreviations of the term. And the external link of PUBMED provides a quick search of PubMed literature to help quickly target literature reports related to this rice trait.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we integrated three existing rice trait terminology set, including TO, WTO and funRiceGene, to construct a comprehensive rice trait ontology, RTO. Meanwhile, an online RTO data service web page is released for quickly browsing of term information and external links for RTO.

Furthermore, there are still some work need to be continue. First, there are other ontologies that may also include rice trait concepts, including CO320, PO et. al., and they also need to be investigated and integrated into RTO to ensure a more complete ontology structure and coverage of rice trait. second, although the RTO is already covered most of the rice traits, with the development of rice research, more and more rice trait concept will need to be integrated into RTO, thus RTO will be an evolving and expanding terminology set, similar to TO and WTO. Third, RTO can be used to guide the knowledge discovery related to rice trait, such as semantic similarity based methods for automated extraction of rice trait mention in literature, and mining their relations with genes, similar work has been investigated on the wheat ontology.

In summary, the construction of RTO provide a standardized terminology set of rice trait, and which benefit for normalization and application of rice trait in various rice studies. Meanwhile, the knowledge discovery based on RTO will serve to automated rice knowledge mining and experimental guidance of rice breeding.

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